

Concept Versus Reality: a Critical Analysis of The Contradictions and Limitations of BRICS

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Abstract

BRICS has had various literature written on its criticisms, but they are mostly from a Western point-of-view. This paper, from a citizen of a BRICS member state, employs the top-down framework of analysis to critically engage with the contradictions and limitations of BRICS since its inception. Adopting the side-ways approach of state-to-state relations, the paper argues for a change in the unipolar world order instead of the collapse of it.

Keywords: BRICS; Anti-Hegemony; Chinese Imperialism

Introduction

Communism. Anti-Western values. These are the criticisms most of us have heard when we talk about BRICS. These, however, are criticisms from America, and they are not constructive, but rather dismissive. Every work in progress needs constructive criticism in order to better itself, and this paper will try to give such from the perspective of a South African student who supports BRICS as a concept and wants to tackle the structural contradictions that limit its success. The paper will lay out the current global juncture, including the many crises, BRICS' attempt to solve them and the limitations it faces, and finally, suggest some solutions to bring the institution closer to its vision.

A Crisis Of Crises? The Current Global Juncture

The state of the world today is very turbulent, with multiple crises taking place at once. For a start, there is the ongoing economic crisis, which has seen the 2008 financial crises, recessions, and countries going into deep debt. Secondly, we have the global health crisis, with examples like the Covid19 pandemic which happened not too long ago. Thirdly, the geopolitical crisis, which I would argue is the cause of most of these crises. Geopolitically, we are facing a crisis of hegemony, a crisis of authority, the American informal empire, and structural power (Garcia, 2025). This leads to the fourth crisis, the global migrant crisis, which consists of citizens seeking refuge elsewhere, not being welcomed, and other problems that arise with it. In the grand scheme of things, I would argue that this is all due to a global governance crisis, as a lack of proper governance globally affects international, national, and local governance.

Most, if not all of these crises stem from capitalism and its shortfalls, and this has resulted in new terms being studied to investigate the contradictions of capitalism and its effects (which give way to multiple crises occurring at once, oftentimes being interconnected). This phenomenon has been coined the 'polycrisis', which is understood as a way of making sense of and bringing solutions to the contradictions of capitalism (Gurcan, 2019). Since these crises are tied to the power and influence of the United States on the global stage, BRICS set itself to become an alternative to the current system. Scholars argue that BRICS itself is a by-product of the polycrisis (Gurcan, 2019), and its main agenda is to become a reformed IMF, which would in this case mean an IMF without US power and influence.

The Birth Of BRICS

The inception of BRICS in 2009 came with a potential new horizon, promising plans of new currencies, an anti-hegemonic world order, and the decentralization of the US imperial power, replaced by multipolarity. Founded on several pillars, BRICS served not only as a by-product of the polycrisis, but as a possible solution to it. One of the pillars was to be a financial and institutional alternative, by introducing the New Development Bank (NDB) and

the Contingent Reserve Arrangement (CRA). This challenged the dominance of the World Bank and International Monetary Fund (IMF) as it aimed to provide financial support to the global south without the neoliberal conditions typically imposed by the global north (Gurcan, 2019, p. 8). Additionally, de-dollarization and financial autonomy as one of the pillars served to counter US hegemony through the dollar in global trade (Gurcan, 2019, p. 38). Furthermore, the geopolitical counter-balancing pillar saw BRICS member states calling for a dual strategy of transforming the hegemonic order from within, while also trying to create new mechanisms to bypass US-led hegemonic institutions (Gurcan, 2019, p. 38). The shift in economic production as a key pillar looked at how the centre of global production has shifted towards BRICS, with China outperforming the US in high-technology exports (Gurcan, 2019, p. 42) (high-tech here might refer to weapons, communications technology and artificial intelligence), giving the global south a chance to assert its autonomy on the international stage. Finally, the pillar of normative and discourse shifts serves to promote the shift to a horizontal model of “development cooperation” based on mutual development (Gurcan, 2019, p. 69). This ensures that in times or opportunities of improvement, member states pull each other up as they develop. An example would be the Covid19 pandemic, with states sharing resources to save their citizens, as well as economic assistance to ensure that partners do not fall behind economically while trying to improve the health of their citizens.

A Framework of Analysis: the Top Down and Sideways Approaches

As this is a critical paper, it is important to have a structure of analysis for this “institution”. I could also argue that the lack of a physical manifestation of a structure for BRICS speaks to its perceived illegitimacy by the global north, but that would be another paper. The top-down approach by Ana Garcia (2025, p. 6) looks at the geopolitical disputes among member states from above. I aim to incorporate the sideways approach here, which focuses on the power struggles between nation-states and their corporations. An example of this would be the relationships between BRICS member states and how these small bilateral relations contribute to the general image of BRICS and the member states’ struggle for power. Here, we analyze BRICS’ pursuit of greater economic, political, and military influence relative to the western or northern powers (Garcia, 2025, p. 6.). This section of the paper will delve into the contradictions and limitations of BRICS goals and values compared to the reality of member states’ actions.

Limitations of BRICS

Since coming together in 2009 and adding South Africa as a new member in 2011, BRICS seems to be stuck in a stagnant position of wanting to change the system, but not wanting to put in the work to do so. Using Garcia’s top-down approach to analysis, I will now highlight the troubles between BRICS member states which prevent them from realising their main goal of moving past hegemony and the imperial order of the US. Firstly, I will look at the

internal tensions within BRICS, followed by the protectionism between states and the prioritization of certain states. Lastly, I will look at the shortfalls of the CRA. Initially, the institution was meant to be a reformist initiative, but after the annexation of Crimea in 2014 and the Russian invasion of Ukraine in 2022, evolved to a coalition (Garcia, 2025, p. 4). This coalition can be economic, political, or military, but western media mostly sees it as a political one (Watts, 2025, n. p.).

Internal Tensions

This issue has greatly affected member states' relationships with each other, as some countries within the group have contrasting values, which lead to internal tensions. An example of this would be the tension between Russia and South Africa. In 2022, after the Russian invasion of Ukraine, South Africa's Department of International Relations released a statement calling for Russia to stop the invasion (Ndlovu, 2024, n.p.), who did not receive it well. Knowing that this disconnection would make BRICS look bad, South Africa retracted its statement, reaffirming its support for its partner. Secondly, China and India have been facing growing tensions in the competition for regional influence (Saran, 2025, n.p.). These are not the only tensions, but the idea of so many of these existing threatens the possibility of BRICS reaching its ultimate goal as a unified front. This affects the political arm of this reform, and can also speak to the military influence, because it is evident which country has military influence within BRICS and if the countries do not stand united in times of armed conflict, it will be difficult to support each other militarily.

Protectionism and Gatekeeping

BRICS countries face an unavoidable mutual development issue. Some member states do not want their partners to develop and advance with them, even if they have the means to assist. One might argue that this is not true due to China providing loans and technological developments to 'developing countries', but this is only for the long term benefit of China. This issue was evident during the Covid19 pandemic, where vaccines had been newly introduced. This introduction saw tensions rise between countries who needed the vaccines but could not produce them and countries who possessed them and did not want to share (Itugbu, 2021, n.p.). This protectionism led to more preventable illnesses and deaths in the less fortunate countries, which greatly hindered their economic progress, so this went against the group's pursuit of economic development and influence relative to their northern neighbours.

Prioritization of certain countries (support for Russia vs support for Iran)

Initially, BRICS was supposed to be a group of states who were against a unipolar global system. This is because the United States, using its dollar to stay in power, had instilled fear into states and rendered international organisations like the IMF and UN obsolete due to "soft (coercion)" and veto power. Scholars argue that the BRICS initiative was one based on

the shared values of anti-hegemony or empirical powers, equality and representation for all countries involved, and a shared set of morals (justice and accountability). However, within the group itself, some inequalities in treatment and foreign policy can be observed. It seems the group prioritises some countries over others. An example of this would be South Africa's retracted statement about Russia's invasion of Ukraine immediately after the attack, but having to wait a while to hear anything about the recent attacks on Iran from BRICS. There has been a notable lack of unity within BRICS (Fabricius, 2026, n. p.), although some BRICS countries have been working together on some goals. A joint speech by President Lula of Brazil and President Ramaphosa of South Africa (Nwosu, 2026, n.p.) a few days ago shows just this, a joint effort to increase security but not for the entire group.

On prioritization, it is also important to note that although China is a member of BRICS, the other states' dependency on it might defeat the very purpose of the group, which was to be anti-hegemon. What started as an attempt to de-centre certain states ended up being a reinforcement of the same system, where the power and influence China has over the other BRICS members makes it a hegemon within the group. If their goal of a reformed IMF would come to fruition, it would be an IMF without US power, but Chinese power instead, which would take them back to the beginning. Aside from that, trade, production, and technological development all seem to be in the hands of China and countries have their hands open. This is why some countries join BRICS, hoping to 'leapfrog' into economic, infrastructural and technological development and benefit from China's position as a creditor in the group (Shopov, 2026, n.p.). This kind of dependency is exactly why it has been difficult for BRICS to de-dollarize and escape the power and influence of the United States and global north, which means their pursuit of greater political influence is hindered.

The Contingent Reserve Arrangement

Abbreviated to CRA, this agreement was made between BRICS countries as a form of financial solidarity between states. It aimed to serve as a "financial defense mechanism" (Vasconcelo, 2025, p. 322.) that countries could access if they were in need without being subjected to the neoliberal conditions that the US-influenced IMF would impose on them. In theory, this would be an important step in the liberation from the dependence on the International Monetary and Financial System (IMFS), and it would open doors for de-dollarization. The virtual fund, which was supposed to assist with balance of payments, liquidity, and shortage issues, stands at US\$100 billion (Vasconcelos, 2025), and this very fact is what pushed me to mention the CRA in this paper. It is based on the US dollar, and it limits the CRA's ability to function as it was designed to.

When one looks closer at the limitations of the CRA, one finds a few more issues. Firstly, this arrangement is too closely linked to the IMF and its systems. One of the terms of the agreement is that the country in need is required to make a "settlement arrangement" with the IMF to increase its chances of getting the money (Vasconcelos, 2025, p. 329). This puts them back into the situation they were attempting to avoid by seeking an alternative to the

IMF, and it puts countries in debt while appearing as 'help' from the CRA. This condition leads me to the second limitation of this arrangement: the conditionality of it, the possibility of refusal. Since this is merely a virtual fund based on a commitment, countries could refuse to lend the money they promised to. The politics, leaders, governance or foreign policy of countries could determine whether or not states get the financial assistance they need. Furthermore, even if the country's request was accepted, there are not enough resources. The virtual fund consists of US\$100 billion compared to the IMF, which in 2023 had a capacity for lending of about US\$932 billion (International Monetary Fund, 2025, n.p.), or the Chiang Mai Initiative Multilateralization (CMIM) which has a lending capacity of US\$240 billion (Kim, 2023, n.p.). Lastly, a big limitation of the CRA is that BRICS' lack of a physical institution leads to an absence of independent surveillance mechanisms due to members wanting to avoid surveilling and intervening in their partner states' spending out of respect for sovereignty, which results in no accountability systems, actions, and economic growth.

A Possible Solution: The Bottom-Up Approach

In a shocking turn of events, I will now defend China's hegemonic status in BRICS and advocate for it to use its status to the advantage of the group. For this, I suggest the bottom-up approach of state-by-state cooperation. This looks at how states engage with each other, but I want to argue that we can use this part to bring each other up in order to all become regional hegemonies as a unified group. Although I believe that we are moving towards a bipolar world, with China and the USA fighting for hegemonic status, it is important to note that there is a difference in how these states project themselves onto the world. The USA is perceived as an aggressive "hegemon", often promoting hard power through sanctions and military force. This is considered condign power, which does not reward cooperation but punishes a lack of it. China, on the other hand, is perceived as a 'friend' or helping hand. Their version of "hard" power is using their position as a creditor and investor, which is known as compensatory power. This system does not punish countries who do not cooperate, but rather rewards those who do.

My solution? China should use its soft power to appeal to more countries, which will broaden BRICS's de-dollarization and the main agenda. Having more countries abandon the dollar will make it lose its power, and of course, the USA will not like that and will likely impose sanctions and tariffs. This is where my formula comes in. Using its compensatory power, I propose that China uses its financial means as a safety net and reassurance for the countries who are concerned about the consequences of abandoning US-led systems. This could be done with the help of the CMIM and other contingent funds, which in the long run will bypass the US-led IMFS. I have created a table below of the difference in the interactions of these states with others to show how my suggestion would work.

Difference between China and the United States Image on the International Stage	
USA	China
Hard Power (Sanctions, Military force) Cooperation → No punishment = 0 Non-cooperation → Punishment = -1 ∴ Condign power (subtracts value)	“Hard” Power (Credit, Investment) Non-cooperation → No reward = 0 Cooperation → Reward = +1 ∴ Compensatory power (adds value)
∴ China (and BRICS countries) should make the reward for joining them greater than the punishment for leaving US-led systems.	

Using the sideways approach I suggested, China, in partnership with the BRICS countries, would quickly get this off the ground, covering each other financially when the tariffs inevitably hit, and showing the rest of the world that it is possible to recover from US subordination. These multilateral relations will eventually build to make the members regional hegemony, which would give them the power to assist others and give way for mutual development, which would then enable the group’s goal of economic, political and military influence rivalling that of its northern counterparts.

Conclusion

This paper brought forward a very loaded suggestion, with potential for multiple areas of divergence for further research. I would suggest that scholars look more into the history of Chinese rule and investigate the possibility and implications of Chinese imperialism. Scholars might argue that it is better to risk the devil we know than the one we have only ideas of, and my response would be that we will know the devil at some point, why not take the initiative while we still have a choice? My argument might seem contradictory, but it is important to note that we are in a Realist Capitalist system; one that thrives in chaos, violence, and power. If we do not play the game, the game plays us.

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